

Properties of Light

Investigation of the Interaction of Light with Media

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Abstract – *The wave properties of light were verified in a series of experiments that utilize elements of different refractive index, lens elements that focus or magnify images, and the interference of light was verified using a diffraction grating of preset number of slits. The behavior of light in the cases of reflection and refraction is governed by the refractive indices of the two media according to the laws of reflection and refraction. The results were found to be in good agreement with the theory. As for the interaction of light with lens, the law of lens was found to be in good agreement with the experimental results. Finally, the interference of light was verified through a Young’s interference setup. The pattern formation was found to be in agreement with the conditions of formation of bright and dark fringes, thus the interference and wave nature of light was verified.*

Keywords: reflection, refraction, interference, convex lens, concave length, diffraction grating.

1 Introduction

1.1 Experimental Objective

1.1.1 Light Reflection & Refraction

To understand the reflection and refraction laws by the use of lasers and a prism thus obtaining the refractive index of the prism³.

1.1.2 Lens action

To measure the focal length of convex and concave lens³.

1.1.3 Interference/diffraction of light

To understand the interference of light phenomenon by setting up an instrument according to Young’s interference device where a laser of a certain wavelength is used to create an interference pattern³.

1.2 Experimental Background

1.2.1 Light Reflection & Refraction

Light entering a medium of refractive index n_2 from a medium of refractive index n_1 experiences partial refraction and reflection, where θ is the angle of incidence, θ' is the angle of reflection, and θ'' is the angle of refraction, in the case of reflection, the relation $\theta = \theta'$ (1) applies. While in the case of refraction, the relation $\frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \theta'} = \frac{n_2}{n_1}$ (2)¹.

A limiting case is when light travels from a medium of higher refractive index to one of lower refractive index, if the angle of incidence occurs beyond the critical angle θ_c , total reflection occurs, since in total reflection the angle of refraction is equivalent to 90° , the relation becomes $\sin \theta_c = \frac{n_2}{n_1}$ (3), in case the second medium is air ($n_2=1$), then the critical angle can be deduced² (figure 1)

$$\theta_c = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{n_1}\right) \quad (4)$$

Figure 1 Reflection and refraction of light. Reprinted from Hillis, D. M. (2014). Walker, J., Halliday, D., & Resnick, R. (2011). *Fundamentals of physics*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley²

1.2.2 Lens action

The behavior of light passing through a lens configuration is governed by the lens formula $\frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} = \frac{1}{f}$ (5), where a is distance between the object and the lens, b is the distance from the lens to the image, and f is the focal length of the lens. Magnification is defined as the ratio of the length l of the image to the length o of the object, this is equivalent to the ratio of the aforementioned distance b to the distance a according to the relation $m = \frac{l}{o} = \frac{a}{b}$ (6), as show in figure 2¹.

Figure 2 The configuration of a lens. The distance s_1 is equivalent to a , and the distance s_2 is equivalent to b . Reprinted from Hillis, D. M. (2014). Walker, J., Halliday, D., & Resnick, R. (2011). *Fundamentals of physics*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley²

1.2.3 Interference/diffraction of light

Due to the wave behavior of light, light passing through a double slit can be modeled after $E_1 = E_0 \sin \omega t$ (6), while the light from the second slit is $E_1 = E_0 \sin(\omega t + \varphi)$ (7), where E is the energy of the light, ω is the angular velocity, t is the time, and Φ is the phase difference between the two waves. According to wave theory, when the two waves converge on the face of the screen, the two waves experience interference. The intensity of the interference pattern is determined via $I = 4I_0 (\cos \beta)^2 \left(\frac{\sin \alpha}{\alpha}\right)^2$ (8), where $I_0 = |E_0|^2$ (9), $\beta = \frac{\pi d}{\lambda} \sin \theta$ (10), $\alpha = \frac{\pi a}{\lambda} \sin \theta$ (11), therein a is the width of the slit, d is the spacing between the slits and λ is the wavelength of the incident light (figure 3)¹.

Figure 3 The optical path of two light waves from the slits to a point on the screen. Reprinted from Hillis, D. M. (2014). Walker, J., Halliday, D., & Resnick, R. (2011). *Fundamentals of physics*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley²

Since the optical path difference is δ and is equal to $\delta = d \sin \theta$ (12), two interference types are observed; constructive interference with $\delta = m\lambda$ (13); and destructive interference, with $\delta = (m + 1/2)\lambda$ (14), where $m=0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots$

For a bright fringe of the m^{th} order, the wave length of the source is

$$P_m = R \tan \theta_m \approx R \sin \theta_m \approx R \theta_m \approx R \frac{m\lambda}{d} \quad (15)$$

In the case of a single slit diffraction grating, the interference phenomenon occurs where the single slit acts as a source of multiple waves that self-interfere and thus an interference pattern can be observed on the screen (figure 4). The spacing of the m^{th} interference pattern is governed by the relation²

$$P_m \approx R \frac{m\lambda}{a} \quad (16)$$

Figure 4 Single slit interference. Reprinted from Hillis, D. M. (2014). Walker, J., Halliday, D., & Resnick, R. (2011). *Fundamentals of physics*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley²

2 Materials & Methodology

A. Materials³

Material	Count
Light source	1
Laser (650nm)	1
Diffraction grating	1
Convex lens	1
Concave lens	1
Arrow target	1
Screen	1
Ruler	1
Track	1

B. Methodology³

2.2.1 Light Reflection & Refraction

Set up the experiment as indicated in figure 4. For a certain incidence angle,

the corresponding reflection and refraction angles are recorded. The incidence angle is varied and the recording is repeated for various incidence angles.

Figure 5 experimental setup of the reflection/refraction experiment. Reprinted from “Experiment 2-8 Properties of Light” lab guide, P.1-P.20, Seoul National University Physics Department (2015)³

2.2.2 Lens action

The device is set up as show in figure 5. The lens is adjusted so that the image of the object is clearly seen on the screen. The distances (a,b,f) required for the calculation are noted. The distances between the lens and the light source is adjusted until another clear image is formed and the readings are recorded. The above procedure is repeated after adding a concave lens to the setup (figure 6).

Figure 6 experimental setup for convex lens experiment. Reprinted from “Experiment 2-8 Properties of Light” lab guide, P.1-P.20, Seoul National University Physics Department (2015)³

Figure 7 experimental setup for concave lens experiment. Reprinted from “Experiment 2-8 Properties of Light” lab guide, P.1-P.20, Seoul National University Physics Department (2015)³

2.2.3 Interference of light

The experiment is setup as shown in figure 7. The distances relevant to young’s double slit experiment are noted (the interval between two fringes of the same state). The grating is switched to a single slit grating and the procedure above is repeated.

Figure 8 experimental setup of the double/single slit interference experiment. Reprinted from “Experiment 2-8 Properties of Light” lab guide, P.1-P.20, Seoul National University Physics Department (2015)³

3 Result

Wavelength of the Diode Laser: 650nm.

3.1.1 Light Reflection & Refraction

Table 1 The results of reflection/refraction experiment. The ideal refractive index of prism is calculated to be 1.585, which is within range of technical data for crown glass.

Angle of Incidence (θ)	Angle of Reflection (θ')	Angle of Refraction (θ'')	$n = \frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \theta''}$
10°	8.5°	5°	1.99

Angle of Incidence (θ)	Angle of Reflection (θ')	Angle of Refraction (θ'')	$n = \frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \theta''}$
20°	18°	12.5°	1.58
30°	27.5°	19°	1.53
40°	38.5°	24.5°	1.55
60°	59°	34°	1.548
Actual Ref indx. =1.585	Avg. Ref. indx. =1.639		Error =3.4%

Table 2 Critical angle calculated from the findings of the refraction experiment.

Series	θ _c (by measure)
1	30.166°
2	39.26°
3	40.81°
4	40.17°
5	40.24°
Average	37.5°
Theoretical value	39.12°
Error	4.14%

3.1.2 Lens action

Table 3 Measurements for a convex lens of 6.5cm focal length.

series	a (cm)	b (cm)	m (cm)	f (cm)
1	8.5	28.5	3.35	6.547
2	6.5	49	7.54	5.739
3	7.5	75.5	10.07	6.822
Avg.	7.5	51	6.99	6.369
			Error	2.01%

Table 4 Measurements for a concave lens of -15cm focal length.

a1 (cm)	b1 (cm)	a2 (cm)	b2 (cm)	f (cm)
13	10.5	-9.5	29	-14.1
11.5	9.0	-8	16.5	-15.5
10.5	7.5	-6.5	12	-14.1
↓AVG↓				
11.7	9	-8	19.2	-14.6
Error				2.66%

3.1.3 Interference/Diffraction of light

Table 5 Results for the interference/diffraction experiment.

item	single slit (diffraction)	double slit (interference)
Slit width	0.16mm	0.08mm
Slits spacing	-	0.25mm
slit & sensor distance	660mm	660mm
pattern # (m)	#2	#2
distance from the center to the mth pat- tern	5.5mm	3.5mm
Source wave- length (calcu- lated)	666nm	662nm
Error	2.46%	1.85%

4 Discussion

While the results for all the experiments were found to be within 4% error of the calculated theoretical values, the expected reasons for the deviations are discussed.

A. Conducting manual readings

Since the ruler/protractor used to record lengths/ angles in the experiment is operated manually, the effect of human error of reading and approximation of reading can lead to error in the calculations. The protractor is divided into divisions of 1 degree, and thus when the inbound/outbound rays coincided with a division the result can be said to be accurate but the case for most of the measurements included approximations for the simplification of the data recording procedure.

B. The elements on the track being non horizontal

The protractor plate as well as the diffraction grating are supposed to be at a perfectly horizontal position for the simplification of the calculations, the alignment with the laser beam was manually adjusted and thus some misalignment is expected which in turn could affect the findings of the experiment.

5 Conclusion

The laws governing the behavior of light in the cases of interaction with different media through reflection and refraction, the path and behavior through lenses, and the interference/diffraction of light waves was experimentally verified by use of an experimental setup that utilizes a source laser and target screen and the elements to be tested placed in between. The findings of the experimental runs were all found to be within 4% error of the theoretical values calculated for each case via formulas 2, 4, 15, and 16. Two sources of error were identified. The first being conducting the reading manually and human bias and the second being the limitation of the experimental setup not being in a completely horizontal placement. A larger sample size can resolve the first issue and a recalibration of the experimental

setup can lead to a more favorable placement for the devices that insures that they're placed in a completely horizontal position.

References

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